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Abbreviations

ALE	Adaptive Laboratory Evolution
AF	Scrubbing water after filtration
AR	Scrubbing water after reformer
BHI	Brain Heart Infusion medium
CIB	Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas
DSM	German Collection of Microorganisms
FOA	Fluoroorotic acid
Gm	Gentamycin
IPTG	Isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactoside
Km	Kanamycin
OD	Optical Density
Syngas	Synthesis gas
RCA	Reinforced Clostridial (Agar) medium
TAG	Triacylglyceride
TGB	Tryptone Glucose Beef medium
TSB	Tryptic Soy Broth medium
YT	Yeast Tryptone medium
YTF	Yeast Tryptone Fructose medium

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Executive Summary

The main objective of Work Package 3 (WP3) is to develop at lab scale a two-stage biological gas-to-liquid process for the conversion of CO₂/CO/H₂ (syngas) produced by gasification into medium (C14) and long (C16-18) chain triacylglycerides (TAGs) that will be upgraded to biofuels.

Deliverable D3.2 has covered two major goals:

- a) To identify the best acetogenic bacterial strain able to produce acetate based on the produced syngas composition and the presence of possible inhibitors.
- b) To genetically modify the selected acetogenic bacterial strains in order to increase its acetate production.

Several acetogenic strains were tested as putative candidates to transform syngas into acetate by fermentation (i.e., *Clostridium ljungdahlii*, *Clostridium autoethanogenum*, *Acetobacterium woodii*, *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM 521, and *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM 2955).

After reforming of syngas, the acetogenic bacteria can survive well to the syngas contaminants contained in the scrubbed water (AR water). However, the scrubbed water derived only after syngas filtration (AF water) is highly toxic since it allows only a limited bacterial growth after a large dilution. Therefore, syngas must be reformed to be used as carbon source in the first stage fermentation process.

Moorella thermoacetica has been selected as the most useful strain to produce acetate from syngas. We have tested the *Moorella* tolerance to different concentrations of several pollutants present in the reformed syngas, such as NH₃ (ammonia), HCN (hydrogen cyanide), H₂S (hydrogen sulphide) and benzene. *Moorella* shows a significant tolerance to all of them. Nevertheless, the most critical contaminant appears to be H₂S due to the high concentration in the reformed syngas. Some options to create more tolerant strains by adaptive laboratory evolution (ALE) are envisioned.

Based on metabolic studies we have proposed the modification of *Moorella* by the deletion and overproduction of some specific genes involved in the acetic acid metabolism. A modular synthetic cassette has been designed to allow the creation of 8 different plasmids to create 8 modified *Moorella* strains. Thus, modified *Moorella* strains have been created by using these cassettes and they were tested for the

production of acetate. Under the tested conditions the transformants showed similar acetate production to the wild type strain, indicating that the modifications do not improve the acetate yield. The reasons for such behaviour must be investigated by using different genetic and biochemical tools in order to propose further modifications.

1. Introduction

The main objective of Work Package 3 (WP3) is to develop at lab scale a two-stage biological gas-to-liquid process for the conversion of CO₂/CO/H₂ (syngas) produced by gasification into medium (C14) and long (C16-18) chain triacylglycerides (TAGs) that will be upgraded to biofuels. The first stage of the biological process involves the production of acetate from syngas fermentation and, to fulfil this aim, D3.2 has covered two major goals:

- a.- To identify the best acetogenic bacterial strain able to produce acetate based on the produced syngas composition and the presence of possible inhibitors.
- b.- To genetically modify the selected acetogenic bacterial strains in order to increase its acetate production.

Several anaerobic bacteria named acetogenic (e.g., *Clostridium*, *Acetobacterium*, *Eubacterium*) are able to transform syngas into useful chemicals (e.g., acetate, ethanol, lactate, butanediol, etc.) through the Wood–Ljungdahl pathway (Merli et al., 2021; García & Galán, 2022). Since acetogenic bacteria can secrete this mixture of compounds during syngas fermentation, metabolic engineering and synthetic biology are powerful tools to increase the acetate production and reduce the spectrum of unwanted by-products. In this way, the main product of gas fermentation, i.e., acetate, can be used as substrate for a second fermentation stage to produce TGAs.

Depending on the feedstock and the gasification conditions, syngas might contain apart from CO, CO₂ and H₂ a number of toxic contaminants (e.g., H₂S, COS, CS₂, NO_x, NH₃, HCN, C₂H₄, tar, etc.) that can inhibit the fermentation process when the amount of these toxic compounds exceeds certain limits. Therefore, it is necessary to select acetogenic bacteria that not only can not only produce high amounts of acetate, but also can tolerate high concentrations of these toxic compounds. The use of the tolerant bacteria will facilitate the gasification of different feedstock in different operational conditions that can render variable amounts of contaminants since it will not be necessary to carry out complex and costly cleaning processes of syngas.

On the other hand, an efficient transformation of syngas into acetate requires to funnel the carbon metabolism to the secretion of acetate as the main or unique product. This means that the production of undesired by-products such as acetone, lactate, ethanol, and other alcohols, must be reduced or eliminated by creating mutant strains with a reduced capacity to secrete these undesired by-products. The technologies currently

used to improve the producer strains are mainly based on conventional random mutagenesis and selection procedures that are grounded in typical trial and error methodologies. The aim of this project is to apply a more rational approach by implementing the construction of recombinant strains based on the use of new tools and technologies provided by systems and synthetic biology. This approach should allow us to construct complex mutants that will have an extremely low probability of being generated by random mutagenic approaches. Thus, the aim was to develop and use systems metabolic engineering tools to improve the capacities of the selected acetogenic strains.

2. Screening and selection of acetogenic bacterial strains

Several acetogenic strains were tested as putative candidates to transform syngas into acetate by fermentation. The strains tested were:

- 1.- *Clostridium ljungdahlii* (CIB collection)
- 2.- *Clostridium autoethanogenum* (CIB collection)
- 3.- *Acetobacterium woodii* WB1 DSM 1030
- 4.- *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM 521
- 5.- *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM 2955

These strains were cultured in anaerobiosis in different liquid media such as RCA, BHI, TSB, TGB and YTF to determine their growing capacities (Figure 1). *Acetobacterium* was cultivated at 30 °C, *Clostridium* species were cultured at 37 °C; however, *Moorella* is a thermophilic bacterium that grows at 65 °C. The results of these experiments are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. Bottles used to culture anaerobic bacteria.

Table 1. Growth of acetogenic bacteria in liquid media determined by measuring the Optical Density (O.D.) at 600 nm at the corresponding time (h). (-) Means that the strain does not grow. Bottles (100 mL) were filled with 80 mL of media using 20 mL of head space filled with N₂ (1.8 atm). Culture media (RCA, BHI, TSB, TGB, YTF) are described in the annexes.

Strains/Media	RCA	BHI	TSB	TGB	YTF
<i>Clostridium ljungdahlii</i>	0.8 (72 h)	0.8 (48 h)	-	-	1.5 (24 h)
<i>Clostridium autoethanogenum</i>	-	-	-	-	3.0 (48 h)
<i>Acetobacterium wodii</i>	-	-	0.6 (24 h)	-	-
<i>Moorella thermoacetica</i> DSM521	-	-	1.0 (24 h)	-	-
<i>Moorella thermoacetica</i> DSM2955	-	-	0.8 (24 h)	-	-

The results of table 1 indicate that although the clostridial strains are able to grow on several rich media, YTF medium appears to be the best medium to grow these acetogenic clostridial strains. On the other hand, *Acetobacterium* and *Moorella* show a narrower range of possibilities to use rich media. In fact, this is the first time that *Moorella* was able to grow in a rich medium such as TSB.

Based on these data we have tested the production of acetate in the three best growing strains using syngas (40:40:10:10. CO:H₂:CO₂:N₂) as carbon source in 100 mL bottles. *C. autoethanogenum* was cultured in YT medium. *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 and *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521 were cultured in TSB medium. The results of these experiments are shown in table 2.

The production of acetate was determined using the Acetic Acid Assay Kit (Megazyme) or by HPLC (see annexes).

Table 2. Production of acetate from syngas using the acetogenic strains in YT (*Clostridium*) and TSB (*Moorella*) media.

Strain	OD ₆₀₀ (time)	Acetate (g/L)
<i>Clostridium ljungdahlii</i>	0.62 (7 days)	1.5
<i>Clostridium autoethanogenum</i>	0.61 (7 days)	1.6
<i>Moorella thermoacetica</i> DSM521	1.05 (7 days)	2.6
<i>Moorella thermoacetica</i> DSM2955	1.18 (7 days)	2.7

The results of table 2 suggest that *Moorella* strains are better acetate producers than *Clostridium* strains, at least under this culture conditions. Figure 2 shows that *C. autoethanogenum* was able to consume more than 50% of CO while CO₂ concentration increased. It is important to notice that these experiments are performed using sealed bottles and that the behaviour in a bioreactor can be different.

Figure 2. Consumption of gases and production of acetate by acetogenic strains. Syngas (100 mL head space, 1.8 atm initial pressure). *Clostridium* was cultured in YT medium plus 3 mM cysteine. *Moorella* was cultured in TSB medium plus 3 mM cysteine. Colour code: **Black**: initial pressure, **Green**: *Clostridium ljungdahlii*, **White**: *Clostridium autoethanogenum*, **Orange**: *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM521, **Blue**: *Moorella thermoacetica* DSM2955.

Figure 3. Production of acetate along with the growth curves of acetogenic strains growing in fructose and syngas. *C. autoethanogenum* was cultured in YT medium. *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 and *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521 were cultured in TSB medium.

The acetate production of selected acetogenic strains was also followed by the growth curve in different growing conditions with syngas and fructose as carbon source. Figure 3 shows that the addition of fructose increases the biomass, but does not increase significantly the production of acetate in the presence of syngas.

3. Identification of the best acetate producer strains based on the tolerance to the contaminants present in syngas

One of the aims of WP3 is to determine the effects of contaminants of syngas in the viability of bacterial strains used for syngas fermentation. We have initially tested the

effect of the contaminants of syngas retained in scrubbing water obtained after filtration of syngas (AF) or after a reforming process (AR) (Figure 4). It is worth to mention that AF and AR samples were obtained from VTT in the framework of bench scale gasification tests (T3.1) as was described under D3.1.

Figure 4. Samples of AR and AF scrubbing waters.

To test the effect of syngas contaminants on the growth of acetogenic strains, *Clostridium* strains were cultured in YTF medium while *Moorella* strains were cultured in TSB medium for 72 h. AR and AF fractions were added to the media in different proportions. The results of these experiments are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Toxicity analysis of AR and AF scrubbing waters added to the culture media. NG = no growth. The OD_{600nm} of the culture was determined after 72 h.

Strain / Medium OD _{600nm}	YTF/TSB in control water	YTF/TSB in 100% AR water	YTF/TSB in 100% AF water	YTF/TSB in 50% AF water	YTF/TSB in 20% AF water
<i>C. ljungdahlii</i>	3.0	2.7	NG	NG	0.3
<i>C. autoethanogenum</i>	3.1	2.8	NG	NG	0.3
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM 521	1.0	0.8	NG	NG	0.3
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM 2955	1.1	0.8	NG	NG	0.3

In addition, we have also tested the AF toxicity using two model aerobic bacteria, i.e., *Escherichia coli* W and *Pseudomonas putida* KT244 growing in LB medium in the presence of 50% AF. Under aerobic conditions these bacteria were not able to grow in this medium (data not shown), strongly reinforcing the observation about the high toxicity of AF on bacteria even under aerobic conditions.

The results of these experiments show that after reforming of syngas the acetogenic bacteria can survive well to the syngas contaminants even using media containing the AR water that contains even higher concentrations of contaminants than those present in the syngas. However, the AF water is highly toxic since it allows only a limited bacterial growth after a large dilution. Therefore, syngas must be reformed to be used as carbon source in the first stage of the fermentation process.

On the other hand, we have tested the tolerance of acetogenic bacteria to specific contaminants still present in the syngas after reforming. Figure 5 shows the growth of the acetogenic bacteria in the presence of 9.35 mM NH_4Cl , 2.5 mM benzene or 6.5 mM Na_2S . The results indicate a clearly different response of the strains depending on the contaminants. Interestingly, it can be observed that in general the strains can be adapted to the contaminants after a lag phase. This observation suggests that most probably the strains can be evolved by adaptation (ALE) to create mutants more tolerant to the contaminants if required. In any case, the *Moorella* strains appear to be more resistant to the contaminant than the *Clostridium* strains.

Figure 5. Effect of syngas contaminants on the growth of acetogenic bacteria. The final concentration of contaminants was: 9.35 mM NH_4Cl , 2.5 mM benzene and 6.5 mM Na_2S .

To test in more detail the limits of tolerance of *Moorella* strains to syngas contaminants after reforming we carried out other experiments using different concentrations of the contaminants in cultures in TSB medium. The results of these experiments can be observed in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Effect of syngas contaminants (HCN, benzene and H₂S (Na₂S)) on the growth of *Moorella* strains.

The results of these experiments indicate that *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521 is more resistant than *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 to HCN and Na₂S (equivalent to neutralized H₂S), because it grew with 1 mM HCN and up to 2 mM Na₂S. On the other hand, both strains grew in the presence of 1 mM benzene. We have also determined that *Moorella* strains are able to grow even with 1 M NH₄Cl (data not shown).

Considering these experiments, we can conclude that the concentration of H₂S is the most critical contaminant factor for bacterial growth. According to the contents of syngas contaminants provided in deliverable D3.1, and assuming that H₂S of syngas

is accumulated in the culture medium as Na_2S after its neutralization, in the case of *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521, it will be possible to provide up to 100 L of syngas per L of culture without any significant risk to the viability of the strain. The *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 would tolerate well only up to 50 L of syngas. Therefore, in continuous cultures it will be important to handle the putative accumulation of Na_2S in the culture medium.

4. Improving the selected strains using metabolic engineering.

According to the previous results we decided to select *M. thermoacetica* strains as the preferred strains to carry out the production of acetate from syngas. Moreover, there is an extensive literature that supports this selection (Sakai et al., 2005; Hu et al., 2016; Bengelsdorf et al. 2018; Redl et al., 2020). Therefore, we have developed a metabolic engineering strategy to improve the production of acetate by modifying the metabolism of these strains using genetic and metabolic engineering tools. To fulfil this aim we had to implement different tools that are described below.

4.1 Construction of *E. coli* recombinant strains expressing three DNA methylases from *M. thermoacetica*

Due to the DNA restriction systems that bacteria use to avoid bacteriophages attack, it is usually very difficult to transform a bacterial strain with exogenous DNA that has not been previously methylated. Because of that we have constructed an *E. coli* strain carrying three DNA methylase genes of *M. thermoacetica* encoded by four genes (Jensen et al., 2019).

The genes *MOTHA-c17610* (*hsdS*), *MOTHA-c17620* (*hsdM*), *MOTHA-c24230* and *MOTHA-c23800* of *M. thermoacetica* encoding the three DNA methylases have been synthesized and cloned in the vector pIZ2 that has the replication *pBBR1*-origin. The resulting plasmid named pIZMethylases was transformed in *E. coli* DH10B to generate *E. coli* DH10B (pIZMethylases). This recombinant strain is resistant to gentamycin and expresses the DNA methylases under the control of the IPTG (Isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactoside) inducible *P_{tac}* promoter. The sequences and maps of the genes and plasmids are shown in the Annex.

The strain *E. coli* DH10B (pIZMethylases) is used as a host to methylate the plasmids that are going to be used to transform *M. thermoacetica* as described below. These

The modular design of our recombinant cassette allows us to construct different cassettes with different gene combinations. In all cases, the *acsA* gene will be deleted and the acetate cannot be transformed back into acetyl-CoA.

Cassette 1.- ACSA-Gm^R-*pduL-ackA-aatA*-ACSA: this is a complete cassette which carries the genes encoding the phosphotransacetylase, the acetate kinase and the acetate exporter. This strain should accumulate a higher concentration of acetate inside the cell that should be exported to the medium.

Cassette 2.- ACSA-Gm^R-*pduL-ackA*-ACSA: this cassette lacks the transporter, so this strain should accumulate a higher concentration inside the cell. Then, the only way to prevent acetate toxicity is by increasing its own mechanisms to export this compound or by growing slower in order to manage acetate accumulation.

Cassette 3.- ACSA-Gm^R-*pduL*-ACSA: this cassette only carries the acetate exporter, so virtually all the acetate produced inside the cell should be exported. This is another strategy to increase the metabolic flux inside the cell towards acetate without overexpressing any other gene of the acetate pathway, and at the same time avoiding toxicity problems.

Cassette 4.- ACSA-Gm^R-ACSA: this cassette would generate an insertion mutant in which *acsA* is only replaced by the GmR encoding gene. This mutant should also generate a higher amount of acetate since it cannot be transformed back to acetyl-CoA.

The insertion of the gene cassettes will create the following changes in the metabolism (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Insertion cassettes created to inactivate the *acsA* gene that encodes the acetyl-coenzyme A synthetase. The *pduL*, *ackA* and *aatA* genes encode the phosphate propanoyltransferase, acetate kinase, and acetate exporter, respectively. Gm^R encodes the gene that confers resistance to gentamicin. The genes are expressed under the control of the P_{G3PDH} promoter. The size of the arrows and the bold letter indicates higher acetate production.

However, we are not sure if the deletion of *acsA* gene will have a huge impact in the central metabolism of *Moorella*. To solve this eventual problem, we have also designed the cassettes to change the flanking regions by the homologous regions to the *pyrF* locus.

Cassette 5.- $PYRF-Gm^R-pduL-ackA-aatA-PYRF$: this cassette is equivalent to cassette 1, but inserted in *pyrF*.

Cassette 6.- $PYRF-Gm^R-pduL-ackAk-PYRF$: This cassette is equivalent to cassette 2, but inserted in *pyrF*.

Cassette 7.- $PYRF-Gm^R-pduL-PYRF$: This cassette is equivalent to cassette 3, but inserted in *pyrF*.

Cassette 8.- $PYRF-Gm^R-PYRF$: This cassette is equivalent to cassette 4 and will generate an insertion mutant in which *pyrF* is only replaced by the Gm^R encoding gene.

All these mutants would be uracil auxotroph and resistant to the uracil analogous 5-FOA (5-fluoroorotic acid). The insertion of these cassettes will create the following changes in the metabolism (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Insertion cassettes to inactivate the *pyrF* gene that encodes the orotidine 5'-phosphate decarboxylase. The *pduL*, *acaK* and *aatA* genes encode the phosphate propanoyltransferase, acetate kinase, and acetate exporter, respectively. Gm^R encodes the gene that confers resistance to gentamicin. The genes are expressed under the control of the P_{G3PDH} promoter. The size of the arrows and the bold letter indicates higher acetate production.

These mutant strains would have lower acetate production than the previous ones because in this case the acetyl-CoA synthetase (*AcsA*) is still functional and some acetate will be transformed back into acetyl-coA.

The genes used to modify *M. thermoacetica* have been synthesized according to the codon usage of *M. thermoacetica* (see annexes) and cloned into plasmid pK18mobSacB originating the plasmids described in Table 4.

Table 4. Plasmids generated to modify *M. thermoacetica*

Plasmid	Genotype
pK18ACSACassette Complete (1)	$\Delta acsA$, Gm^R , overexpression of <i>pduL</i> (phosphate propanoyltransferase), <i>acaK</i> (acetate kinase) and <i>aatA</i> (acetate exporter) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.
pK18ACSACassette PudL-AckA (2)	$\Delta acsA$, Gm^R , overexpression of <i>pduL</i> (phosphate propanoyltransferase) and <i>acaK</i> (acetate kinase) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.

pK18ACSACassetteACSA AatA (3)	$\Delta acsA$, Gm ^R , overexpression of <i>aatA</i> (acetate exporter) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.
pK18ACSACassette GmR (4)	$\Delta acsA$, Gm ^R
pK18PYRFCassette Complete (5)	$\Delta pyrF$, Gm ^R , overexpression of <i>pduL</i> (phosphate propanoyltransferase), <i>acaK</i> (acetate kinase) and <i>aatA</i> (acetate exporter) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.
pK18PYRFCassette PudL-AckA (6)	$\Delta pyrF$, Gm ^R , overexpression of <i>pduL</i> (phosphate propanoyltransferase) and <i>acaK</i> (acetate kinase) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.
pK18PYRFCassette AatA (7)	$\Delta pyrF$, Gm ^R , overexpression of <i>aatA</i> (acetate exporter) with P_{G3PDH} promoter.
pK18PYRF cassette GmR (8)	$\Delta pyrF$, Gm ^R

4.3 Transformation of *M. thermoacetica* with recombinant plasmids.

The plasmids shown in table 4 were used to transform *M. thermoacetica* by electroporation (Figure 10) after being previously methylated as described in 4.1.

Figure 10. Electroporator.

The *M. thermoacetica* cells were electroporated following the protocol described in Annexes and according to published procedures (Iwasaki et al., 2013; Kita et al., 2013a,b; Rahayu et al., 2017; Jensen et al., 2019; Kato et al., 2021). The transformants were selected after the electroporation using a liquid culture medium containing Gm (gentamycin).

Using this protocol and the plasmids described in table 4 we have been able to obtain the following transformants:

- 1.- *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521 pK18ACSACassette complete (1)
- 2.- *M. thermoacetica* DSM 521 pK18ACSACassette AatA (3)
- 3.- *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 pK18ACSACassette PudL-AckA (2)
- 4.- *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 pK18ACSACassette AatA (3)
- 5.- *M. thermoacetica* DSM 2955 pK18PYRFCassete Complete (5)

Although the low efficiency of the transformation procedure has not allowed to obtain all possible transforms, the collection of obtained transformants provide enough material to test the behaviour of these new strains concerning the acetate production. Nevertheless, the transformants are under production to this study (see future actions).

4.4 Analysis of the acetate production by *M. thermoacetica* transformed strains.

To determine the acetate produced by the *M. thermoacetica* transformed strains, these strains were cultured in TSB medium containing gentamycin and the productions have been compared with the acetate production of wild type strain in TSB medium without gentamycin (Table 5).

Table 5. production of acetate by the *M. thermoacetica* strains. Experiments were done by triplicate.

3 days culture	
Strain	Acetate (g/L)
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955	6.72 ± 0.43
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18PYRFCassette complete (5)	7.38 ± 0.08
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18ACSACassette PudL-AcaK (2)	7.14 ± 0.62
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18ACSACassette aatA(3)	6.91 ± 0.03
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521	7.83 ± 0.04
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521 pK18ACSACassette complete (1)	6.51 ± 0.01
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521 pK18ACSACassette aatA (3)	6.77 ± 0.08
7 days culture	
Strain	Acetate (g/L)
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955	7.37 ± 0.31
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18PYRFCassette complete (5)	7.76 ± 0.21
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18ACSACassette PudL-AcaK (2)	7.65 ± 0.16
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM2955 pK18ACSACassette aatA (3)	7.77 ± 0.05
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521	8.06 ± 0.01
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521 pK18ACSACassette complete (1)	7.25 ± 0.10
<i>M. thermoacetica</i> DSM521 pK18ACSACassette aatA (3)	7.16 ± 0.20

The results of these experiments show that the modified strains of *Moorella* resistant to gentamycin do not increase the production of acetate when compared to the wild type strain, at least in the tested conditions. Since there are many metabolic reasons that can explain such behaviour, these reasons will be investigated in order to take future actions. It is worth to mention that the current results performed in bioreactor have shown that the production of acetate is already very high in the wild type strain of *Moorella* and very close to the theoretical maximum yield, and perhaps the bottlenecks in the acetate production are not the expression of the proposed genes. Because of that, we have to change our metabolic approach to better identify these bottlenecks.

5. Conclusions

- 1.- *Moorella thermoacetica* has been selected as the most useful strain to produce acetate from syngas.
- 2.- For the first time, we have been able to grow *Moorella* in a rich medium like TSB that allows the production of high concentrations of biomass.
- 3.- It has been determined that syngas has to be reformed to avoid the high concentration of contaminants that appear in the scrubbing water only after filtration of syngas.
- 4.- The *Moorella* tolerance to different concentrations of several pollutants present in the reformed syngas, such as NH₃ (ammonia), HCN (hydrogen cyanide), H₂S (hydrogen sulphide) and benzene has been tested. *Moorella* shows a significant tolerance to all of them. The most critical contaminant appears to be H₂S due to the high concentration in reformed syngas. Some options to create more tolerant strains by adaptive laboratory evolution (ALE) are envisioned.
- 5.- A recombinant *E. coli* carrying three DNA methylases from *Moorella* has been created to favour the transformation of *Moorella* strain using the methylated plasmids.
- 6.- Based on metabolic studies we have proposed the modification of *Moorella* by the deletion and overproduction of some genes. To fulfil this task a modular synthetic cassette has been designed that allows the creation of 8 different plasmids to create 8 modified *Moorella* strains.
- 7.- Several modified *Moorella* strains have been created by using the cassettes and tested for the production of acetate. Under the tested conditions the transformants showed similar acetate production, indicating that the modifications do not improve the

acetate yield. The reasons for such behaviour must be investigated by using different genetic and biochemical tools in order to propose further modifications.

6. Future actions

In order to improve the results obtained under WP3 we propose the following future actions that will be reported in an updated version of D3.2 or even within other deliverables of WP3 such as D3.4 “Optimization of syngas fermentation process parameters for acetate production (1st stage)”:

1.- We will develop protocols for ALE evolution in order to improve the tolerance of *Moorella* to syngas contaminants. This will allow the growth of cells under continuous culture operational conditions in case of having a high accumulation of these contaminants in the culture medium due to the recirculation of high amounts of syngas.

2.- We will analyse in deep by using genetic and biochemical protocols the reasons why the created transformants do not increase the production of acetate in order to propose further actions and metabolic changes. It is important to identify the bottlenecks of acetate production under extreme fermentation conditions. In this way we will use omic tools to try to identify these bottlenecks.

3.- We will test the possibility of increasing the overproduction of enzymes in *Moorella* by increasing the copy number of the genes introduced in the strain by using plasmids. Although to the best of our knowledge the transformation of *Moorella* with plasmids has not been tested yet, we believe that the plasmids used to transform *Clostridium thermocellum* (Groom et al., 2016), a closely related strain (Rabemanolontsoa et al., 2017), will be useful for this aim. Thus, we will test the usefulness of these plasmids to create new *Moorella* recombinants. In case of success, the use of plasmids will facilitate the studies in order to reach new metabolic improvements.

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Annexes

Protocol for electroporation of *M. thermoacetica*

The *M. thermoacetica* strains were cultured in the TSB medium and harvested by centrifugation (6,000 g for 10 min at RT) at an optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) of 1. The cells were then washed and resuspended in sterile water.

The methylated pk18mob plasmids carrying the cassettes were extracted and purified from the transformants of *E. coli* DH10B (pIZMethylases, pk18mobcassettes) strains. These plasmids were used for the transformation experiments

Plasmids were introduced into the *M. thermoacetica* strains by electroporation using a BIO-RAD Gene Pulser 220V (Model n°: 1652077). Plasmid DNA (2-5 µg) was added to 200-µl cell suspensions in an electroporation cuvette with a 2-mm gap. The cells were pulsed at 1.5 kV, 600 Ω, and 25 µF and immediately inoculated into 20 ml of TSB medium with CO₂ (20%) plus H₂ (80%). The cell suspension was then incubated at 55°C for 24 h and inoculated into a 20 ml of TSB medium with CO₂ (20%) plus H₂ (80%) and 10 µg/ml gentamycin during 5-7 days. The culture was inoculated into the same medium and now the clones were able to grow in 48 h.

Analysis of acetate by HPLC

Acetate concentration was measured by HPLC (Agilent 1260 Infinity II) using a refractive index detector and an Aminex HPX-87H column 300mm x 7.8 mm (BIO-RAD), at 55°C. Ultrapure water containing 5 mM sulfuric acid was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min.

RCA Medium

Reinforced Clostridial Agar (RCA) is an enriched non-selective medium intended for the cultivation of *Clostridia* and other anaerobic and facultative bacteria from various clinical and non-clinical specimens.

Composition:

- Tryptone 10 g/L
- HM peptone / Beef extract 10 g/L
- Yeast extract 3 g/L
- Dextrose (Glucose) 5 g/L
- Sodium chloride 5 g/L
- Sodium acetate 3 g/L

- Starch, soluble 1 g/L
- L-cysteine hydrochloride 0.5 g/L
- Agar 13.5 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 6.8±0.2

BHI Medium

Brain Heart Infusion Broth is recommended for the cultivation of fastidious pathogenic microorganisms. Brain Heart Infusion Broth has been used as culture medium for *Streptococcus pneumonia*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Leishmania promastigotes* and *Clostridium difficile*.

Composition:

- Beef heart (infusion from 250g), 5 g/L
- Calf brains (infusion from 200g), 12.5 g/L
- Disodium hydrogen phosphate, 2.5 g/L
- D(+)-glucose, 2 g/L
- Peptone, 10 g/L
- Sodium chloride, 5 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 7.4±0.2

TSB Medium

Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) is a nutritious medium that will support the growth of a wide variety of microorganisms, especially common aerobic and facultatively anaerobic bacteria.

Composition:

- Casein peptone (pancreatic), 17 g/L
- Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, 2.5 g/L
- Glucose, 2.5 g/L
- Sodium chloride, 5 g/L
- Soya peptone (papain digest.), 3 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 7.3±0.2

TGB Medium

Thioglycolate Broth with Resazurine is a nutritious medium for sterility testing of biologicals and for cultivation of aerobic and anaerobic organisms. Any increase in the oxygen content is indicated by a color change of redox indicator resazurin to red.

Composition:

- Agar, 0.75 g/L

- Casein enzymic hydrolysate, 15g/L
- L-cystine, 0.50 g/L
- Dextrose, 5.50 g/L
- Resazurine, 0.001 g/L
- Sodium chloride, 2.5 g/L
- Sodium thioglycolate, 0.50 g/L
- Yeast extract, 5 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 7.1±0.2

YTF Medium

Routine medium growth for *Clostridium ljungdahlii* DSM 13528

Composition:

- Yeast extract, 10 g/L
- Bacto tryptone 16 g/L
- Sodium chloride 4 g/L
- Fructose 5 g/L
- L-cystine, 0.50 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 5.8 ± 0.2

YT Medium

YTF medium without fructose

LB medium

Miller's LB is a highly-referenced microbial growth medium used for the cultivation of *E. coli*. This nutrient-rich microbial broth contains peptides, amino acids, water-soluble vitamins, and carbohydrates.

Composition:

- Tryptone 10g/L
- NaCl 10 g/L
- Yeast Extract 5 g/L

Final pH (at 25°C) 6.5 - 7.2

Sequences of DNA methylase *MOTHA-c17620 hsdM* gene from *Moorella thermoacetica* codon optimized for expression in *E. coli*.

```
ATGACTGAAAACACAAATATGGATCTATCAACGCTGGAGAACTGGCTGTGGGAAGCTGCGTG  
CGTCATCCGCGGTGCAGTGGACGCCCCGAAGTATAAAGACTACATCCTGCCCTGATTTTCC  
TGAAACGCCTCTCCGATGTTTTTCGAGGACGAAATCGCTCGTTTGGCGGAAGAGATCTTTGAC
```


AGCATCGAAGAAGCTCTGAAGCAGGTTGAGGAGGACCACGCCCTCGTGCGCTTCTACATTCC
 GCCTCAGGCACGTTGGGATGCAATCAGCCGCCAAACTACGAACATCGGCGAATATTTGACTT
 CCGCTGTGCGTGCTGTGGCACGGGAAAACCCGAAGCTGCATGGTATTTTTGAAAATATCGAC
 TTCAATGCGCAGATGGCGGGTCAGCCGGTGATGATAACGAcCGTCTTTACAACCTCATTCA
 AGTTTTGTGCGGCCATCGTCTGGGTCTGAAGGACGTCGAGGTGGACATCCTCGGCCGCGCCT
 ATGAGTACCTGTTGAGAAAGTTTGCAGGGCCAGGGCCAAAGCGCAGGGGAATTTATAACC
 CCGCGCGAGGTTACCTGGCTTATGGCGTACCTGTTAGAGCCGCGTCCGGGTGACGAGATCTA
 CGACCCGGCCTGCGGTTCTGGTGGCCTGTTGATTAAGAGCGTGTGGCGCTGAAGGAGACGT
 ACGGCGACGATCCGCGTATTGCACCGGTTAAAATCTATGGTCAAGAAATCTTGTACACGACC
 TTCGCCATGGCTAAGATGAACGCATTTATCCATGATCTGGAGGCGGATATCCGTCTGGGTGA
 TACCATGGCGCGTCCGGCGTTTACCAATCCAGATGGTTCACCTGCGTACCTTCGACAAAGTGA
 CCGCGAATCCGATGTGGAATCAAAAATCCCCGCTGCCGCTATACGAGGAGGACCCGTTTGAC
 CGTTTCAAATTTGGCGGCATTCCACCGGCATCTAGCGCGGATTGGGGTTGGATACAGCACAT
 GTTTGCCTCGCTGAAAGAAGGTGGCAAGATGGCGGTTGTTCTGGATACCGGTTCCGTCAGCC
 GCGGCTCCGGTAATCAGGGTAGCAATCGTGAGCGCGATATTCGTAAGGTGTTTCGTGGAGAAC
 GATCTGGTTGAATGTGTGATCCTGCTGCCGAAAACATGTTCTACAACACCACCGCGCCAGG
 CATCATTATGGTTATCAACAAAGCAAAAAACACCCGGCGGAAATCTTCTGATTAACGCgA
 GCAAACCTATTCACCAAAGGTCGTCCGAAAACTATATGGAAGACGAGCACATTAAGCAGGTC
 TATAGCATCTACCGCGAATGGCGTGAAGAAGAGGGCCTGAGCAAGATTATCCGGTAGAGGA
 GGCGGCGGTAATGACTATAACCTGTCTCCGAGCCGTTATGTTAGCATTAAACGGCAAGGAGG
 AATACCGTCCGATTGAAGAGATCTTGGTGGAACTGGCGGAGGTTGAAGAGGAACGTCAAGCG
 GTTGACAAAGAGTTGAATGATATCTTGGGGAAGCTGGGTTTTGGTGGCTGGCTGAACGGCTA
 A

Sequences of DNA methylase *MOTHA c17610 hsdS* gene from *Moorella thermoacetica* codon optimized for expression in *E. coli*.

ATGGGAAAAGAAGTAAATGAAGTTAAGGAGGGCTATAAGGAAACGGAGATCGGCGTTTTGCC
 AGAAGACTGGGAGGTTGTTTCGTCTGGGTAAGGTGTTTGAAGAAGTTGATCGTCGCGTGAATA
 ACGTGAAGAACGCCGCGAGCCTGCCGGTGCTCTCCCTGACTAAAAACAACGGCATTATCCCT
 CAGACCGAACGTTTTAAAAAGCGCATTGCGACGGACGACCTCAGTAACTATAAGGTGGTCTA
 CAAGAAAGAGCTGGTTTACAATCCGTATGTGATCTGGGAGGGTGCCATTTCATATTCTGAATC
 GCTTGGAGGCGGGTTTAGTTAGCCCGGTTTACCCGGTCTTATCTGTAAACAAAAGGTGGCC
 GACGCATACTTCTTTGATTTCTGGCTGCGCACCCCGAGCGCAATTAAGGCGTACAGCCGTTA
 TGCAAGCGGTGCTGTGAACCGCGTCTGCTATCCGTAAGACCGATTTCAAAAATATCGATG
 CTCCGTTACCTCCGCTGCACGAACAGCGCAAAATTGCGTACGTGCTGAGCACCATTCAAAGA
 GCGATCCAACCTGCAaGATAAAGTTATTGCGGCAACCCGTGAGCTGAAAAAGTCCCTGATGCG
 CCACTTGTTCACCTATGGTCCGGTgCCGGTGGACCAGATCGACCGTGTTCGGTTGAAAGAGA
 CAGAGATCGGCATGGTTCCGGAACATTGGGAGGTTGTTCCGGCTGCGTGAAGTGGCAGACTTT
 ACCAAGAAGCCGCGTGGTCTGAACTATTCTGGCAATATAACCATTTCATTCCGATGGAACCTGAT
 CCCCATCGGCCGTGTCAACATTCAAAAATACATCATCAAACCGTCGAGCGAAATTTGAGCG
 GGGTGTACTGCGAACAAGGTGATCTGCTCTTGGCTAAAATCACCCCGTCTTTGAGA ACTAC
 AAACAGGGTATTATCTCACAGATCCCGAAACCGTTTGCCTTTCGACCACTGAGGTGTACCC
 GATCAAGGCGCGTAAGGACTTCCTGGAGATTCTGTATTTGTTCTATTACTTGCTGATTCCGC
 AGGTTCCGCCAGGATATCGCTGGTAAGATGGAAGGCACCACGGGTGCTCAACGCATTAGCAAA
 AGCGTAATCCAGAATTACCTGATCCCGATCCCGCCGTTGTCTGAACAACGCCAAATCGCGCG
 TTTCTGATTACCGTTGATAAAAAAATTGAAGCCGAAGAGTATCGTAAGTCCACCCTGCAAA
 GCCTGTTCCAGACGATGCTGCACCTGCTTATGACCGGCAAGGTGCGCGTGAAAGACCTTGAG
 GTCAAAGAGGACGCGCTGCGTCAGTAA

Sequences of DNA methylase *MOTHA c24230* gene from *Moorella thermoacetica* codon optimized for expression in *E. coli*.

ATGACAATTGAAAGGAATTTTGATATAGCTTTCGTGCGGACCTCGCGCTTCACGAAAAGCA
AATCCAACAGAATTATAGACCTATTATCGCGGTGCACAAATGGTTTGCCTCGCCCTGGTA
CTCTGTTTCGTAGCCTGTTGCTGGCGGAGTTCGCTCAGGGCAACTTGGCCGATAATTA
CGTTCACATAACTTTCAGGGTTGAAGGTAGCGGACCCCTTCATGGGTGGCGGCACCCCGCT
GATCGAGGCGAACCCTGGGTGTGTCACATCCTGGGCTACGATATCAACCCGATGGCTTACT
GGATCGTTCGTGAGGAGATTGAACATCTGAACCTCGAAGCgTACCAACAAGCAGCACGGGAA
GTTGGCTTCTCCTGGAAGAAAAGGTGGGTCCGTTTTATCGTACGCGCTGCCCGATTTGCGG
CCGTCAAGACGCGTTGGTTAAATACTTCTTATGGGTAAAGTTTACCAGGTGTCACA
ACTGCGGCCGTGAGTTCGATCTGTTCCCGGGCTACGTGCTGGCGCAGAAGGGcCGACATCCGAAAGAT
GTTATTATCTGCTCGACCTGTGGTTCTCTGAACGAGGTGGGCGACAAGCGCAACCCGGGCCA
CTGCCACA
ACTGCGGTGAAGAGTTGAAAACCAAGGCCCGGCGGTTCGCAACCAATGCCCGT
GCCCGCATTTGTGGTGTGCGTAATAGCTACCCGGACCCGGAGAGCGGTCCGCCGGGT
CATCGTATGGTTGCTATCGAATATCACTGtAGCTACTGCAAACCGGAGCACCGCGGCCGTTTTTTTAA
AAAACCGGATGCCGACGACCTGGCGAAATTCGCTACTGCGGTCCGTACGTGGGAAGCGCTGC
AaCCGCAGTTTGTGCCGGAGGAGAAGATTCCGGCAGGGCGACGAGACAAACCGTCTGCATCGT
TGGGGTTACC
GCTATTATCGTGAGATGTTTAAACGAGCGCCAATTGCTGGGTTTGGAGCTGCT
GGCGCGTAAAATCAGCCAGCAACCGGATGAGCGCATTAAGAACGCCCTTGC
GACCAATCTGTCCGATCTGCTGCGCTACCAAAACATGTTATGCCGTTATGATCCATATGCGTTGAAATCCTTG
GACATCTTTTCCGTGCACGGCTTTCCGGTCCGGTCTGATCCAATGCGAATCTAACATGCTGGG
GATTCCAGGTGGTAAAACGGGCCTGAATATCGGTTCCGGTGGCTGGACCAACATCGTGGACA
AGTACCTGAAGGCGAAACACTATTGCCAGTGGCCGTTTCGAAATCCGCCATGTTAATGGTCGC
AAACGTCAGCTGTGGATTAAGGGCGAGTGGATTGGCGAACGCAGACAAGGAATGACCCAGCA
GCGTGAGGTTGATCTCCGCTGCGCAAGCGCAACCACTGCGTTTCTGAAGCCGAGCAGCTTAG
ACGCCGTTCTGACCGATCCGCCTTATTTTCGCGAATGTTTCAGTATGCAGAACTGATGGACTTC
TGCTATGTTTGGCTGCGTCGTCGTTGGTGGGTGCCTCCAATCCAGTCTTCACCCCGCGTACGAC
CCGCAACCCAGAAGAGTTGACCGGTAATACCACGATGAGCCGTGGCATCGACGACTTCACCG
GTGGACTGAGCCGTGTGTTTAGCAACATGGCTGCTGCTCTTAAGCCGGGCGCGCCATTCGTG
TTTACGTACCACCATAATCGTCTGGAGGCCTATTACCCGGTTGCTGTGGCGTTGCTTGATGC
GGTCTGGCATGTACCGCAACCCTGCCGTGTCCGGCTGAAATGGCGGCATCGATCCATATTA
ACGGCACCGGCAGCAGCATCATTGATACCGTGTTCGTGTGCCGTACGACCGGCGTCTGTCT
CGTCGTCGCTCGTGAAGAACCGGAACAGATTGCGGCGCTGATCATCAAAGAACTAGAGGA
ACTTGAGAAAGGTGGCGTTCCGGTTACCCGCGGTGACACCCGATGTATTATCTATGGTCACC
TGATACGTTTGGCTGTTTGGTATCTTCGCGCAACCTGGGACAAAAATCTGTCTTGGGATAAG
AAGTTCGCCCTCATTGCGCGTATGATTGATGAGCTGGGTGGCGCGGGCGCGATTGAAACCTA
CTTGAAGAGAACGGTGTCCAGCTGAAGACCCGTGCGGAAACCATTTGTATGTGAAGGCGAAT
CTGAATACGGCGCAGGTGGT
GACGAAGTGTCTTTTTAA

Sequences of DNA methylase *MOTHA c23800* gene from *Moorella thermoacetica* codon optimized for expression in *E. coli*.

ATGCCCATGCCAGTACTATCAGTTGAACAACGTAACAAGCTGGAAAGAACAGTTGTTGAAGC
GCGCGATGTCGCGGAGGCCGGTGCGAAAGCCGCGTTGGAGGCGCTTGCGGTGCATACCACG
AGCCGTA
CTCATATGACCCCGGAGCAGCGCCGTTTGAAGAAATCACCTGAGAGCCAGAGCG
CGCCA
ACTGGGCGACCGTCAAGACCAGCGTGGCAAGATGGAAATCACGCATCTCATTCAAGA
GTGGGCATATGAACATTGGCATCGTATGTTGTTTCGCCCGGTTCCCTGGCAGAGAACGACCTGC

TGATCGAACCGGAGATGGGTGTGGCGGTTAGCCTGGAAGAATGCGGCGAACTGGCCCAAGAA
GAGGGCACCGATCTGTGGACGCTGGCGTCTCGTTTTCGCTCAGCAAATGCTGCCCCAGATATT
TAGACCTGATGACCCGGTGCTGCAAGTGACCTTCGCGCGTGAATACCAGCTTAAGCTGGAAC
AGCTTTTGAACGACTTGGAGCCGGGTATCTTCAAGGCCTCCGATGCATTAGGCTGGGCGTAC
CAGTTTTTGGCAGAGCAAACGTAAGAAACAAGTCAATGAAAGCGGAAACAAAATCGGTGCGGA
CGAATTGCCAGCAGTTACGCAGCTGTTACCGAACCGTACATGGTTAACTTTCTGATTTCATA
ATACGATTGGCGCCTGGTATGCGGGTAAGGTGCTGGCGGAGAACC CGCAATTGGCTGGCCAG
GCAGAGTCCGAAGAGGAGCTGCGCCGTGCTGTGGCGTTGCCGGGCGTTACTTGGGATTACCT
GCGTTTTCGCCGCTCTGGTGACGGCGAAGGTCCTGGCGTCCGGCAGCTGGCACTTTTGAAG
GTTGGCCTCAACGTGCAGCGGAGCTGAAGATCCTGGA_cCCGTGCTGCGGTAGCGGCCACTTT
CTGGTCGCGACCTTTTATCACCTAGTGCCGATCCGCATGGCAGAGGAGGGCCTGACCGCAG
TGAAGCCTGCGACGCTGTGCTGAGCGATAATCTGCATGGTCTGGAGATCGATGAACGTTGTA
CCCAGATCGCAGCGTTTTGCTCTCGCGTTAGCGGCTTGACCTACCCGGGTGCGGGTGGTTAT
CGTCCGCTGCCGGGTCTGAGGATTGCTTGCTCGGGTATCGCGCCAAATACCAAAAAAGAAAA
CTGGCTGGCCCTAGCGGGTGACGACGAACGCTGCGAAACGGTATGGCACGTCTGTACGATT
TGTTCCGCGAAGCACCGATCTTAGGCTCTCTGATTGATCCGGGGTCCGCACTTGAGAACAAC
CTGATCGAGGCTGGCTTTGATGAACTGCGTCCGCTGTTGGAGAAAGTAATGAGCGCAGAGAA
GGACGACTACGAGCAGCATGAGCTCGGCGTAGCCGCGTGCAGTATCGCTGATGCGGTTTACA
TTCTTTCCGGCCGTTATCATTGGTCAATTACGAACGTGCCGTACCTGGCTCGTGGCAAGCAG
GGTGTGTTCTGAAGAACTATCTGGATACCCACCACGCGCGCTCTAAGCAGGACCTGGCCAC
CGCGTTCATCGAGCGCAATCTGATGCTGTGTCTGGAGGGTGGTAGTACCGCGCTGGTGACGC
CGCAACAATGGTTGTTCCAAACCGGTTATAGCAAGATCCGTAAAAAACTGCTGCGTGACCTG
CGTTGGGAGCTCCTGGCCATCTTGGGCGAGCACGCGTTCCGCAGCTCTGAAGCGGCTGGTGC
GTTCCCGGCGATTTATGTTTTGTAGCAAACCTTTGCCGAAAGATAACCACCTGTTTTTTAGCA
TCAATGTTTCCGAGCGCAGCTCAGCGTGCAGCAAAGACTTGTACCTGCA_aCACGCTTCGCTG
AATAAGATGCAGCAAATCAGCCAGCTTAAGAACC CGGAGCACATTATTATACCAATACCTT
CAGCGGCTTTTCGCGTGTGGTACTACGCAGATTGTTATCAAGGTATTAGCACCCGGTGACA
ACCCGCGTTTTCTGCATTAAATTCTGGGAACGCCATCGATCCTGCCGGGCTGGGAACGCTTC
CAGACCCCGCCTGAGGAAACCCAATATTACGGCGGCCGTGAACACCTGATCCGTTGGGAGGA
GCGCGCCAGCATAAAGAGTTAGGCGCGATTTCGTGGTAAAAATGCGTGGGGTAAGTGGGGCA
TCGTTATTGGTGTGACTGCCAGTAA

Map of plasmid pIZMethylases

Sequences of the genes used to modify *M. thermoacetica*

Sequence of homologous region up to *pyrF* (*MOTHA_c09230*) gene

CGCGGCCTCCTCAATATTCAATTTGTCATCCACCGGGGCGAGGTCTACGTCTGGAGGTAAATCCCGTTCAGCCGCACGGTACCCTACCTCTCCAAGATTACCGGCGTGCCCATGGTGGCCCTGGCCACCAACGTCATGCTGGGCAAAGCCTGCCGGAGCAGGGCTACCGGGCGGCTTAATGCCCGCCGGATTTTACCGCCGTAAAGGTCCCCGTCTTTTCTTCGGCAAGCTGTTGCAGGTGGACACCTCCCTGGGACCGGAGATGAAGTCCACCGGCGAGGTAATGGGGATTGATCCCCGTCTCGAACGCGCCCTCTATAAAGGCCTGGTAGCCGCCGCTGCTCCATCCCCATCACGGCACCCTGCTGGCGACCATCGCCGATAAGGACAAGGCGGAAGCAGTGCCCATCATCAAGGGCTTTGCGAACTGGGCTTCCAGGTGGTGGCTACCGCCGGCACCGCCGGCGCCCTGGCCGCAGCGGGACTCTTCGTAGAGAGGGTGGGGAAGATCCGCGAGGGTTCGCCCCACATTATCGACTATATCCGGGAAGGGAAGGTCCACTTTGTCTCAACACCCTCACCAGGGGCAAGATGCCCGGCCGGGACGGTTTTAAGATCCGCCGCGCCGCGGCGAACTGGGCATCCCCTGCCTGACTTCCCTGGATACGCCCGGGCCCTGCTCAAAGTCTCCAGTCCCTGAAGTCCGGCGACGGGTTTAACCTCAAACCCCTGCAGGAGTATGTACCCCTTTCCCGTCTTAAACGGAGGAGCGCCAAATCGCCTCCGCCCCACCCCGGCAGGAGCAGCAGCCCGGGCTGCACCGGCCGGGCGGTTTCCCGGCCGGCCCTTCAAGCACCAGGCGAGATGGCCGGGCCGCCCATTTAGCATATCAAGAGCGCCGGAAGGGAAGGGCTTTTCCGGTTTTTACCAGTCCGGGTTAAGCCTGACTTAAAGGCGGTACCGGACCCTCCCC

ATATTCACTCCGCTTACACTCCGTTTTTTGAACTATAAGATCATAAAGCGATATTTAAGGGC
TTCTGGCCTGCTTGCCAACACTAATGTACCTGCAGGAGATG

Sequence of homologous region down to *pyrF* (MOTHA_c09230) gene

AATAGAGATGGTCAAATAAATAACTTCGGCCTGCTTTCATGCTTGATAATTTTTGTGCATGTAG
GGCTACAATGATAGTAACAGGTGATGACACGATGGAACGAATTAACCTTTATCAATACCCGGG
AGTTTAAAAATAGAGCAACCCAAATCTTGAGGCAGGTACAAAAAGACCAGGTTATTATTATA
ACCAATCGCGGTAAACCTGTAGCCACTTTAAAAGGTTTCAATCCACGTGACCTGGTTGTTGC
AGAAGATAGACATGATAGCCTTTACCAGCATTGCGGCAACAAATTTAAAAGAAAGTCCAG
AACTGGCTGCCAGGGATACCAGGCAAATCGCCACTGATTTTGAAAAGATAACAGCTAAAATG
AGAAAACAGATTGCCTACAGGACCTGGGAAGAAATGGACCGGCACTTAAAAGGGGATCCTTA
TGATCTTACTGGATACTAATATTTTTTATAATCGATCGTTTTTTTTCCAGGGGATAGTCATTAC
GCTATAAACAAGGAATTCATTCAAGAGTTATCGCGGCTCGAGGCGGGGTTTTCTATTTTTTC
GTTATTAGAACTTACCGGCATTGCTTCTTTTAACCTTTCAGCCAAAGAATTGCAGCAATGGT
TGTTTGATTTTGCCTCCGTTTATCCTATTTCGTATTCTTGATCCCTATGATTTAAAGATTGAT
TCTGCCAAGGAATGGTATACTAAATTTTTGCAGGAACTAATGGCAAAGTTACCCACCAAAT
GACTTTTGGCGACGCTATTTTTTTTACGTGAAGCTGAAGGTTATCAAGTAGAGTATATTATTA
GCTGGAATAAGAAACATTTCTTTCACGTACGACAATCAAAGTGCTCAACCCTGAAGAGT

Sequence of homologous region up to *acsA* (MOTHA_c23020) gene

GCCGGGCCAGAAGAAAGACCTTGACCTCGGCCCCCGGTTCCAGGAGATGGCGGGCGACCACC
AGGCCGTCGCCGCCATTGTTGCCTTTACCACAGAAGATTAAAATCCGGCGGTTGGCTACCTG
GCCCTGAAAGTGGCGCTCGATGGATTCTACCACCCGCAAGCCGGCGTTTTTCCATTAAGACGA
TACTGGGTATCATGTACTCGCTGGACGCCAGGCGATCCAGCTGTCCCATCTCTGCTGCCGTT
ACCAGGTACATGGCTTTAACCCTCTTCCGAAAATGAACTTTCAACCAGAGCTACCGCTGCGG
CGTAAGCGTGGCAGTGGGAGAGACTGACGGTTATCTCACCCACCCCGAGTCCCGGGCCAGC
TGTCGGGCCCCGTTATGGAGGATTACCCGCGGTCGCCACCCCTGTTCCCTGGTGATTTCAAT
ATCTTGCCAGGAACAACGGCCCAGCCCTATCCCCAGGGCCTTCATTACCGCCTCCTTGCCCG
CGAAACGAGCTGCCAGGGAAGCCCCGGGCCGGTGCCGGGCCAGGCAATAGGCTACCTCCGCC
GGTGTAATAACCCTGGCCAGGAGCGGGGGTGGCGTTTTATAGAGCGCTCCAAACGGCTGAT
TTCAATGATGTCTATCCCGGCCCTCTAGCATAATCCCATCCTAACCATTTACCTGCTCCTTAA
TTCCCTTAAAGCTTATTCGGCAACAATGTTGAAAACCTTCTCTTTTTGTAGAAATTAACCTG
GCCGGCAGGACCACTAACAACGCTACATGCATCTGTGCGGCCAGGGACCCGGTCCGGGCGG
CGAAACAACCCGGGTGCGCCCCGAAAAGGACGGCTAAGGCCGCGGACAGGTAAGCCAGGGCC
GTTACCTCCTCCCCTGCCCGCTCAGTCCCCCTATTTACATTTAAGGCCGTCCGGGCGACCT
TTAACGCCGAAAGCCTTTCCTTTTTTTAGTCCCGGCTTAAAGATAGAAATACACGAAGGGAG
TGACCTCA

Sequence of Homologous region down to *acsA* (MOTHA_c23020) gene

ATTTTCTTATTATCTATCTAATATTAAGGAGGGCGGGTATGGGCCGTAAGGTTTACCTGCTT
TTTGCTACTTTAACCATCAGCGAAGTTCTGACGGCAGTACTTTTTTTCCGCGTACCGCCCTT
CCCGGTTTTTCCCTTGCCTTCGTGGTTTTTGAACGCCCTGGGAGCAGGCCTGGCAATATACTTCC
AGGGGCTATCCTGTTCTTTACCCAGCGGCCGATAGAGGAAGACGCCAATTTTAATACTGAC
AGTATTTTTGTCTCCACCCTGCAGATTGCCGACCAGACCCTGCCGGTTTTTACGCGGCGGGTT
AAATAAAACTACGGCGGCCAAAACGGCCGATATAATCCAGGACCTCACCAAGTGCCGGCCA
TAGCCATAACCGACCGGAGCGGGTCTGACCTTCCCTGGGCGTAGGATGCGACCAGCACCAG
GCGGGGACCGGATTCTCACGGAAGCCACCAAAGAGGTCATTGCCACCGGGCGCATGAAGGT
TGTCACACTCCCAGGGCCTCTGCTGCCCCCGGTATGGTACAGGCTGCAATTGTCCCCTGA

AATCGGCGGTTATCGTCCCCCTGAAGTGCCGGGATGAGATTGTTCGGCGCCCTCAAACCTCTAC
CAGACCAGGGAGGGGGTTTTCCAGCCGGAGATTGTCCGCCTGGCCGTCGGCCTGGCCAATTT
GTTGAGCCTGCAGATAGAGCTTCCGAGTTGGACCGCCAGCGCCAGCTCCTCACCGAGGCGC
GGCTGGAGGCCCTCAACGCCAGATTAACCCTCACTTCTTCTTTAATACCCTGAACACCATC
ATTAGCTTCAGCCGGACGGACCCGGAGCGGGCCCGGCGCCTGCTCATCCGCCTGGCCAACT
CTTCCGGCAAACCTTGAGCCGCCACGGCAGCTTGACTACCCTGCAGGAAGAGCTGGATTGTG
TTCGTACCTACCTGGTACTGGAAAAGGCACGCTTCGGCAATAAATTCGGCTACCTTGAGGAC
GTGCCGCCGGAACCTGCTGGAGTACCATATTCCAGTCCCTCAGCCTGCAACCCCTGGTGGAAAA
TGCCGTTAACCATGGTCTGTTGGCCAAAGAAGGGCGGGCAGGTCAGGTATCCGGCCGCC
TGGCGGGCAGCAACTCCACCTGGCCGTCAAGGACGACGGCGTCGGCATCCCGGCCGAAAAG
ATCAACCTGGTGACGCAACCGG

Sequence of *P_{G3PDH}* promoter

GGACGGTTGCCAAGTACCGGGACGAGCAGGGCATCCCGGCGGCGGCTAAAAGAAAACGATAT
TAGTTAAGAAGGATTTTGACCATTTGTGTTGAATAGATAGTGTGTTGACGGTACAATCTCCGG
CAATTAGCAATATATCATAATAAATCCTGATTGGGTTAGGAATAATATCAAAGCCAAGGAG
CCTGAAAGCGGTGGGGGTTGACGCTGCAGGAATTTAACCCCTTGCCGTTACAATAAATATAAG
GAGGAGTACA

Sequence of *GmR* codon optimized for expression in *M.thermoacetica*

ATGCTGCGGAGCAGCAACGACGTCACCCAGCAGGGCAGCCGGCCAAAACCAAACCTGGGCGG
CAGCAGCATGGGCATCATtCGGACCTGCCGGCTGGGCCCCGACCAGGTCAAAtcCATGCGGG
CCGCCCTGGACCTGTTTTGGCCGGGAATTTGGCGACGTCGCCACCTACAGCCAGCACCAGCCC
GACAGCGACTACCTGGGCAACCTGCTGCGGAGCAAAACCTTTATCGCCCTGGCCGCCTTTGA
CCAGGAAGCCGTCGTCGGCGCCCTGGCCGCCTACGTCCTGCCCCGGTTTTGAACAGCCCCGGA
GCGAAATCTACATCTACGACCTGGCCGTGACGCGCGAACACCGGCGGCAGGGCATCGCCACC
GCCCTGATtAACCTGCTGAAACACGAAGCCAACGCCCTGGGCGCCTACGTCATCTACGTCCA
GGCCGACTACGGCGACGACCCCGCCGTCGCCCTGTACACCAAACCTGGGCATCCGGGAAGAAG
TCATGCACTTTGACATCGACCCAGCACCGCCACCTAA

Sequence of *pduL* codon optimized for expression in *M.thermoacetica*

ATGAAACTGAAACAGCCCGGCATCGTCGCCGGCGTCAGCAACCGGCACGTCCACCTGAGCCG
GGAAGACGTGCAAGTCTGTTTTGGCAAAGGCTACACCCTGACCCCATCAAAGACCTGGGCC
AGCCCGGCCAGTTTTGCCCTGCCAGGAAACCGTCATCATCGTCGGCCCCAAAGGCGCCATCGAA
AAAGTCCGGGTCTTGGGCCCCGAACGAAAGAAACCCAGGTGCAAATCAGCCTGACCGACGC
CTTcAAACTGGGCGTCAAACCCCCCGTCCGGGACAGCGGCGACCTGGACAACACCCCCGGCA
TCGTTCATCGTCGGCCCCAAAGGCAGCGTCATCAAAGACCGGGGCGTCATCATCGCCAAACGG
CACATCCACATGCACACCAGCAACGCCGAAAAATACGGCGTCAAAGACAAACAGATCGTCAA
AGTCCTGGTCGAAAAAGAAGGCCGGCGGCTGATCTTTGACGACGTCCTGATCCGGGTCAGCG
AAAAATACGCCCTGGAATTTACGTCGACACCGACGAAGCCAACGCCGCCCTGCTGAAAACC
GGCGACCTGGTCTACATCATCGAAGAATAA

Sequence of *acaK* codon optimized for expression in *M.thermoacetica*

ATGATCGTCCTGGTTCGTCAACAGCGGCAGCAGCAGCATCAAATACCAGCTGCTGGACATGGA
CAACGAAAAAGTCTGTGCAAAGGCCTGGCCGAACGGATCGGCATCCCCGGCAGCCGGATCG
TCCACAAAAAAGCCGGCGAAAAATTTATCGTCGAAAAACCCATGCCCAACCACGACGAAGCC
CTGAAAATCGTCTGGAAGTCTGAAAGACGAAAAACTGGGCGCCATCAAAGACTTcAAAGA
AATCGACCGCGTCGGCCACCGGGTTCGTCACGGCGGCGAAAAATTTAGCGGCAGCGTCTCTGA

TCGACGACGAAGTCATCAAAGCCATCGAAGAATTTAGCTACCTGGCCCCCTGCAtAACCCC
CCCAACCTGATGGGCATCAAAGCCAttATGAAACTGCTGCCCGGCGTCCCCAACATCGGCGT
CTTTGACACCGCCTTTCACGCCAAAATGCCCGAAAAAGCCTACCTGTACGCCATCCCCTACG
AATTTTACGAAAAATACAAAATCCGGCGGTACGGCTTTCACGGCACCAGCCAtCGGTACGTC
AGCAAACGGACCGCCGAAATCCTGGGCCTGGACTACAACAAAGCCAAAATCGTACCCTCCA
CCTGGGCAACGGCGCCAGCATCGCCGCCGTCAAAAACGGCAAAGCGTCGACACCAGCATGG
GCTTTACCCCCCTGGAAGGCCTGGTCATGGGCACCCGGAGCGGCGACCTGGACCCAGCATC
GTCACCTTTCTGATGGAAAAAGAAGGCCTGAGCGCCGAAGAAGTCTACACCATCCTGAACAA
AAAAAGCGGCGTCCTGGGCCTGAGCAAAAACCTTTAGCAGCGACATGCGGGACATCGAAGACA
AAGCCCTGGAAAACGACCCCTGTGCCGGCTGGTCTTGGACATCTACGAATACCGGATCGCC
AAATACATCGGCGCCTACGCCGCCCATGAACGGCGTCGACGCCATCAGCTTTACCGCCGG
CGTCGGCGAAAACAGCCCCATCACCCGGGAAGAAATCTGCGTCAACTACCTGAGCTTTCTGG
GCATCAAAATCGACAAAGAAAAAACAACGTCAAAGGCGAAGAACGGATCATCAGCACCCCC
GACAGCAAAGTCAAAGTCTGGTCGTCCCCACCAACGAAGAAGTCTGATGATCGCCCGGGACAC
CAAAGAAATCATCGAAAAAGGCCTGAAACAGCTGGAATACTAA

Sequence of *aatA* codon optimized for expression in *M. thermoacetica*

ATGGCCCACCCCCCTGCTGCAtCTGCAGGACATCACCTGAGCCTGGGCGGCAACCCCCT
GCTGGACGGCGCCGGCTTTGCCGTCCGGCCGGGGCGAACGGCTGTGCCTGGTCGGCCGGAACG
GCAGCGGCAAAAGCACCCCTGCTGAAAATCGCCGCCGGCGTCATCCAGCCCGACAGCGGCAGC
GTCTTTGTCCAGCCCGGCGCCAGCCTGCGGTAAtCTGCCCCAGGAACCCGACCTGAGCGCCTA
CGCCACCACCGCGACTACGTCTGCGGCCAGATCGGGCAGCCCGACATGGCCTGGCGGGCCA
CCCCCTGCTGGACGCCCTGGGCCTGACCGGCCGGGAAAGCACCCAGAACCTGAGCGGCGGC
GAAGGCCGGCGGTGCGCCATCGCCGGCGTCCTGGCCGCCGCCCGACGTCCTGCTGCTGGA
CGAACCCACCAACCACCTGGACATGCCACCATCGAATGGCTGGAACGGGAACTGCTGAGCC
TGGGCGCCATGGTCATCATCAGCCACGACCGGCGGCTGCTGAGCACCCCTGAGCCGGAGCGTC
GTCTGGCTGGACCGGGGCGTCACCCGGCGGCTGGACGAAGGCTTTGGCCGGTTTGAAGCCTG
GCGGGAAGAAGTCTTGAACAGGAAGAACGGGACGCCACAAACTGGACCGGAAAATCGCCC
GGGAAGAAGACTGGATGCGGTACGGCGTCACCGCCCGGCGGAAACGGAACTCCGGCGGGTC
CGGGAACGGCCGACCTGCGGACCGCCGGAAAGAAGCCATCCGGGCCCGGACCCCTGAC
CCTGAACACCCAGCTGCGGCCCCACCGGAAACTGGTCGCCGTGCGCGAAGACATCAGCAAAG
CCTGGGGCGAAAACAGGTCGTCCGGCACCTGGACCTGCGGATtCTGCGGGGCGACCGGCTG
GGCATCGTCGGCGCAACGGCGCCGGCAAACACCCCTGCTGCGGATGCTGACCGGCCTGGA
CCAGCCCGACAGCGGCACCATCAGCCTGGGCCCCAGCCTGAACATGGTCACCCCTGGACCAGC
AGCGGCGGACCCCTGAACCCCGAACGGACCCCTGGCCGACACCCCTGACCGAAGGCGGCGGCGAC
ATGGTCCAGGTCGGCACCGAAAAACGGCACGTGCTCGGCTACATGAAAGACTTTCTGTTTCG
GCCCGAACAGGCCCGGACCCCGTACAGCGCCCTGAGCGGCGGCGAACGGGGCCGGCTGATGC
TGGCCTGCGCCCTGGCCAAACCCAGCAACCTGCTGGTCTTGGACGAACCCACCAACGACCTG
GACCTGGAAACCCCTGGACATtCTGCAGGACATGCTGGCCAGCTGCGAAGGCACCGTCCTGCT
GGTCAGCCACGACCGGGACTTTCTGGACCGGGTCGCCACCAGCGTCCTGGCCACCGAAGGCG
ACGGCAACTGGATCGAATACGCCGGCGGCTACAGCGACATGCTGGCCAGCGGCACCAGAAA
CCCCTGACCACCGCCAGCGTCGTGAAAACGAACCCACCAAAACCCAAAGAAACACCGCCGC
CCGGGGCCCCACCAAAAAACTGAGCTACAAAGACCAGTTTGCCCTGGACAACCTGCCCAAAG
AAATGGAAAAACTGGAAGCCAGGCCGCAACTGCGTCAAAAACCTGGCAGATCCAGATtTAC
ATGGAAAAAACCCCCGGAGCCTGCGGAACTTTCGGCTGATCTACCGGAGCAGCAAACAGAG
CTGGCAGAACCTGAAAACGCCGGCTGGAACCTGGAATGA

Map of plasmid pK18ACSAcassette Complete (1)

Map of plasmid pK18ACSAcassette PudL-AckA (2)

Map of plasmid pK18ACSAcassette AatA (3)

Map of plasmid pK18ACSAcassette GmR (4)

Map of plasmid pK18PYRFcassette Complete (5)

Map of vector plasmid pK18PYRFcassette PudL-AckA (6)

Map of plasmid pK18PYRFcassette AatA (7)

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Map of plasmid pK18PYRFcassette GmR (8)

